

The Role of Job Satisfaction as Mediating of Financial Compensation and Communication Competence on the Agricultural Instructor Performance

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the impact of financial compensation and communication competence on employee performance. job satisfaction is involved as a mediator. A total of 165 employees were involved as respondents in this research proportionally. Data analysis through structural equation modeling (SEM). The results showed that financial compensation plays a very important role in employee satisfaction and performance. Communication competence also has a positive effect on satisfaction and performance. Satisfaction itself is also the main key that has an impact on improving performance. In addition to being a key factor, job satisfaction also plays a role in connecting financial compensation to employee performance. while on the relationship of communication competence to performance, job satisfaction is considered unimportant. We suggest to the management that in order to improve the performance of agricultural extension workers, financial compensation should get more attention. Likewise, communication competence needs to be improved through employee training and development.

KEYWORDS: Financial Compensation, Communication Competence, job satisfaction and agricultural instructor performance

INTRODUCTION

Development in developing countries is generally focused on the agricultural sector in order to improve the food quality of the population and to meet the national food needs (Ministry of Agriculture, 2014). One of the government's efforts to realize the agricultural sector into an advanced sector is to ratify Law No. 16 of 2006 concerning the agricultural, fishery and forestry extension system in Indonesia. The government realizes the importance of the existence of agricultural extension workers to improve the agricultural sector, because agricultural extension workers are people who directly interact and deal with farmers in rural areas. Agricultural extension is a form of non-formal education that is tailored to the needs and desires of farmers. Agricultural extension activities are carried out to help overcome various problems faced by farmers. Agricultural instructors are directed to carry out the task of mentoring and consulting for the main actors and business actors in developing their agribusiness businesses, so that the adoption of appropriate technology can run well and in turn increase the empowerment of the main actors, production, productivity, income and welfare of farmers and their families.

The identity of agricultural extension workers as a process that produces changes in the behavioral abilities of the community related to agriculture, always faces various challenges in achieving agricultural extension goals. This is a challenge for extension agencies to be able to become resilient institutions, in the sense of having a sustainable identity of existence as well as having a dynamic ability to respond positively to all challenges and obstacles faced, so as to be able to answer the needs of the community, especially farmers, which is also the duty of a farmer. agricultural extension workers, for this reason an agricultural instructor is required to be able to develop his talents and potentials in carrying out his duties as an extension worker so that his performance is maximized.

Assessing the performance of agricultural extension workers is an important decision. Campion et al. (2011) stated that fair performance appraisal is very important to avoid unjustified bias and increase employee objectivity, productivity, and responsibility.

One of the factors that affect the performance of agricultural extension workers is job satisfaction (Parvin & Kabir, 2011). Job satisfaction is a very personal thing, meaning that the only person who can feel it is concerned and its nature is not always the same from one person to another, therefore job satisfaction has always been an important point by organizations because job satisfaction is a criterion to measure success. organization to meet the needs of its members. A low level of

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satisfaction with agricultural extension workers can result in organizational disorganization because they are not motivated to do what is best for the organization, on the other hand agricultural extension workers who get satisfaction in their work will lead to self-motivation to act to achieve individual achievements which will also result in organizational progress.

In addition to the satisfaction factor, extension workers are required to be able to convey information to farmers, so agricultural extension workers must have good communication competence in carrying out their duties. Because the implementation of agricultural extension is carried out in accordance with the agricultural extension program. Competence in technical, conceptual, and human relations skills are also factors that affect the performance of agricultural extension workers. Management of workforce competence includes several competencies such as: communication competence. The influence of competence on performance can be seen from the level of competence which has practical implications in human resource planning, this can be seen from the description that Communication Competence has a significant influence on Employee Performance (Duwit, 2015).

In addition to the communication competence factor, the provision of financial compensation is also a factor that needs to be considered to attract and retain employees, therefore the government, especially in the field of Agriculture, requires it to achieve the goals that have been set. The success of agricultural extension workers in the field is highly dependent on compensation within the organization to attract and retain human resources because the organization needs them to achieve its goals.

The phenomenon related to the performance of agricultural extension workers is currently felt to have begun to decline since the enactment of regional autonomy. Many agricultural instructors have switched functions to become structural officials or remain agricultural extension workers but can carry out their duties properly. In the beginning, agricultural extension workers were central employees who worked in the regions helping and assisting farmers in rural areas. After experiencing changes in the institutional structure with the existence of regional autonomy, currently agricultural extension workers who directly develop farmers are local government officials.

Some Level II regions (districts) consider that agricultural extension workers are not important because they do not directly affect local revenue, so that some skilled workers in agricultural extension workers turn to sub-district employees as administrative staff. Some extension workers become structural officials in local government agencies so that the level of assistance to farmers is decreasing.

This study aims to examine the role of satisfaction in mediating financial compensation and communication competence on the agricultural instructor performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Performance

According to Robbins (2016: 187) employee performance is the result of work achieved by someone based on job requirements. A job has certain requirements to be carried out in achieving goals which are also known as job standards. Assessing employee performance is an important decision among organizations to avoid unjustified bias and increase staff objectivity, productivity and responsibility (Campion et al. 2011). Furthermore, Rahimi & Vazifeh (2011), stated that a strong organizational culture leads to high and effective performance. Organizations that encourage employees to participate in decision making, set goals, and solve problems will have higher performance. Moehersono (2012:11) states that employee performance as a result of performance that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization both qualitatively and quantitatively, in accordance with the authorities, duties and responsibilities of each in an effort to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, does not violate the law and in accordance with morals or ethics. Employee performance is the result of the employee's work during a certain period compared to various possibilities, such as standards, targets or predetermined criteria (Campbell et al., 2010). Thus, the performance of agricultural extension workers can be interpreted as a result of the individual's ability to work in accordance with their duties and responsibilities.

Job Satisfaction

To satisfy staff, companies must provide various facilities to staff such as to free products and services, healthy culture, fairness, provide upgrades and payments to employees because this is the basis, which contributes to employee satisfaction (Parvin & Kabir, 2011). Job satisfaction is a general attitude towards one's job as the difference between the rewards received by officers and the amount of rewards believed to be received, including work, salary, promotion opportunities, supervision and co-workers (Robbins and Judge, 2016). Huang and Liu (2012) define job satisfaction as the gap between actual and expected income compared by personnel with others related to salary increases and promotions according to their service and income

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ratio. According to Bakotić & Babić (2013) job satisfaction is a sense of comfort and positive experience that an employee has related to his work. Job satisfaction shows how much an employee likes his job and his level of preoccupation with work. Job satisfaction can influence work behavior, and through it, organizational performance (Pitaloka & Sofia, 2015). Thus it can be said that job satisfaction is a measure of the feelings that arise from within the workers after comparing the work achieved.

Financial Compensation

According to Mabaso & Dlamini, (2017) compensation is the payment paid by the employer to his employees for the services rendered (e.g. time, effort and skills), This includes fixed and variable salaries associated with performance levels. According to Swanepoel et al, (2014) stated that financial compensation is financial and financial rewards provided by employers for the time, skills, and efforts provided by employees in fulfilling job requirements aimed at achieving organizational goals. Furthermore, according to Absar et al, (2010) reported that employee compensation is one of the main functions of human resource management. Compensation is important for employers and employees to attract, retain and motivate employees. Ardana (2012) states that financial compensation is compensation that is directly in the form of money. So it can be said that, financial compensation is everything that is constituted or considered as a reward to employees in the form of money.

Communication Competence

Communication competence is considered to contain cognitive and behavioral aspects (Rubin, 1985). Understanding that communication competence contains these two aspects, then being informed socially and perceptively is a key factor in becoming a competent communicator. In order to be mutually beneficial to each other in a relationship, communication competence is a necessary tool consisting of cognitive, attitude, emotional and behavioral knowledge (B-Ikeguchi, 2014). To achieve personal, educational, vocational and social goals, communication competence is the main quality that individuals need to achieve success in life (Light & Mcnughton, 2014). Communication competence has been confirmed as a valuable resource for improving employee performance in nursing organizations (Lim et al., 2012). Communication competence is an important means of controlling the conflict environment and a useful resource for reducing nurses' emotional exertion (Park et al., 2015). Thus, communication competence is very important. Smooth communication is the main means to resolve collisions and conflicts between organizational members and is also connected with job performance, so efforts to improve communication in nursing organizations are very important (Lim, Park, & Kim, 2012). Communication competence is a prerequisite for effective leadership, because he found in his study that each leadership dimension is highly correlated with communication competence. (Cetină, & Rădulescu, 2012). Communication competence is about knowledge and wisdom using applicable communication skills. Communication competence is not only understanding good communication skills but also the ability to apply and adapt that knowledge when certain situations may arise unexpectedly (Suher et al. 2016).

Research Framework

From some of the previous research descriptions above, it can be formulated the conceptual framework of this research as follows

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

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Based on the theoretical literature and the results of previous research that have been put forward, in this study put the following hypothesis.

- H₁ : Financial Compensation affects on job satisfaction of Agricultural instructor
- H₂ : Communication Competence affects on Job satisfaction of Agricultural instructors
- H₃ : Job Satisfaction affects on the job performance of Agricultural instructors
- H₄ : Communication competence affects on job performance of agricultural extension workers
- H₅ : Communication competence affects on job performance of agricultural extension workers
- H₆ : Job Satisfaction mediates of the relationship between Financial Compensation and Agricultural Extension Performance
- H₇ : Job Satisfaction mediates of the relationship between Communication Competence and Agricultural Extension Performance

METHODS

The research was conducted on agricultural extension. Determination of the number of samples using the opinion of Hair et al., (2013) where the minimum sample size is 5-10 x the number of indicators. The sampling technique was carried out by proportional simple random sampling so that the number of samples was 165 people. Data collection method with Likert scale based on five ranges Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Disagree, (4) Agree and (5) Strongly Agree, (Rensis Liket, 1932). further testing the data used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Respondent profile

Respondent characteristics	Number of respondents	Percentage
Gender		
Male	106	64,2
Famale	59	35,8
Age		
26-35 year old	19	14,5
36-45 year old	71	43,0
46- 55 year old	59	35,8
56 and above	16	9,7
Education		
High school	16	9,7
Diploma	5	3,0
Bachelor's	140	84,8
Master's	4	4
Income		
Rp. < Rp. 2.000,000 ,-	8	4,8
Rp. 2.000,000 – Rp. 3.500,000,-	82	49,7
Rp. 3.600,000 – Rp. 4.500,000,-	61	37,0
> Rp. 4.600,000 – Rp. 5.500,000,-	14	8,5
Total	165	100,00

Based on the profile of the respondents in this study, it is dominated by men with an age level that is no longer productive, namely 46 to 55 years and an average bachelor's education with a monthly income of Rp. 2,000,000 up to Rp. 3,500,000,- and has been working for more than 10 years.

Table 2. Convergent Validity

	Variable	Estimate	Cut Off	Information
A1	<--- financial compensation	0,738	0,50	accepted
A2	<--- financial compensation	0,738	0,50	accepted

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		Variable	Estimate	Cut Off	Information
A3	<---	financial compensation	0,729	0,50	accepted
A4	<---	financial compensation	0,624	0,50	accepted
A5	<---	financial compensation	0,666	0,50	accepted
A6	<---	financial compensation	0,538	0,50	accepted
A7	<---	financial compensation	0,656	0,50	accepted
B1	<---	Communication Competence	0,786	0,50	accepted
B2	<---	Communication Competence	0,738	0,50	accepted
B3	<---	Communication Competence	0,844	0,50	accepted
B4	<---	Communication Competence	0,682	0,50	accepted
B5	<---	Communication Competence	0,701	0,50	accepted
C1	<---	Job satisfaction	0,617	0,50	accepted
C2	<---	Job satisfaction	0,694	0,50	accepted
C3	<---	Job satisfaction	0,786	0,50	accepted
C4	<---	Job satisfaction	0,744	0,50	accepted
D1	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,715	0,50	accepted
D2	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,723	0,50	accepted
D5	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,697	0,50	accepted
D7	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,622	0,50	accepted
D8	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,815	0,50	accepted
D9	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,621	0,50	accepted
D10	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,729	0,50	accepted
D11	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,735	0,50	accepted
D12	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,576	0,50	accepted
D13	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,561	0,50	accepted
D16	<---	Job Satisfaction	0,515	0,50	accepted

From the table above, it can be seen that none of the indicators has an estimate value below 0.50. So it can be stated that all indicators used in this study can be used to be included in structural testing.

Goodness Of Fit Model

Overall, the Fit Model is acceptable, where the known value of X2 Chi Square is 188.135, which is greater than the Chi Square table value at 292 Degrees of Freedom (DF) as the output of AMOS 24 is significant at 0.05 or (0.05; 292).) obtained 332.854 or (322.026 < 332.854), then the GFI, TLI and CFI values were found to be > 0.90 and the RMSEA value < 0.08. Thus, it can be concluded that the measurement model has met the requirements to prove the hypothesis through the structural model. Hair et al (2010) said that the use of 4-5 criteria of Goodness Of Fit is considered to reflect the feasibility of the model, as long as it includes Goodness Of Fit, namely Absolute Fit Indices, Incremental Fit Indices and Parsimony Fit Indices. So the SEM model of this study was accepted.

Reliability

Reliability analysis can be seen that the Cronbach alpha value for each respondent's perception variable can be seen from several variables, namely the financial compensation variable, communication competence, job satisfaction and the performance of the extension worker having an alpha value above 0.60 so it can be said that all the variables used in the study reliable.

Normality

Univariate normality shown by CR skewness and Curtosis for each variable with a cut off value of ± 2.58 . In the table above, it can be seen that there are no indicators that have CR Skewness and Curtosis values > ± 2.58 . Therefore, it can be concluded that the research data is normally distributed so that further analysis can be carried out.

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Hypothesis Test Result

Table 3. Dirrect Hypothesis Path

Exogenous		Endogenous	Estimate		S.E.	C.R.	Sig
			Unstandar d	Standard			
Financial Compensation	--->	Job satisfaction	0,306	0,423	0,078	3,903	***
Communication Competence	--->	Job satisfaction	0,158	0,225	0,068	2,325	0,020
Job satisfaction	--->	Job Performance	0,386	0,289	0,140	2,750	0,006
Financial Compensation	--->	Job Performance	0,206	0,213	0,096	2,146	0,032
Communication Competence	--->	Job Performance	0,224	0,239	0,084	2,650	0,008

Source: AMOS 24, 2021 Output Results (processed)

H₁ : Financial Compensation affects on job satisfaction of Agricultural instructor

The effect of financial compensation on job satisfaction obtained a Critical Ratio (CR) value of 3.903 which is greater than the cut off value of 1.96 or (3.903 > 1.96) at a significant level *** or less than 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). Thus, it can be stated that financial compensation has a significant effect on job satisfaction. The magnitude of the effect of financial compensation on job satisfaction of agricultural extension workers is 0.423. This means that every 1% an increase in the value of financial compensation, it will increase employee job satisfaction by 0.423%.

These results support previous research conducted by Ardana (2012) which says that compensation is everything that is received by employees as a gift for their contribution to the company or organization. Financial compensation can be divided by direct compensation, such as basic salary and living wages, bonuses, commissions, profit sharing, profit sharing, and share distribution and different payments, namely savings annuities and program share purchases. The provision of financial compensation has an effect on employee performance (M.Baledi & Saed 2017); (Küster & Canales 2011). From these results, the better the provision of financial compensation in the form of a decent salary, performance allowances, health insurance, life, pensions and others, the higher the performance of Agricultural Extension.

H₂ : Communication Competence affects on Job satisfaction of Agricultural instructors

The influence of communication competence on job satisfaction obtained a Critical Ratio (CR) value of 2.325, greater than the cut off value of 1.96 or (2.325 > 1.96) at a significant level of 0.020 or less than 0.05 (0.02 < 0.05). Thus, it can be stated that communication competence has a significant effect on job satisfaction. The magnitude of the influence of communication competence on job satisfaction of agricultural instructors is 0.225. This means that every 1% there is an increase in the value of communication competence, it will increase employee job satisfaction by 0.225%. These results support previous research conducted by Duwit, (2015) and Yu & Ko (2017) management of workforce competence includes several competencies such as: communication competence. The influence of competence on performance can be seen from the level of competence which has practical implications in human resource planning, this can be seen from the description that Communication Competence has a significant influence on employee performance. From these results, the more employees have skills in communicating with the community, the more they will improve their performance as Agricultural Extension Officers.

H₃ : Job Satisfaction affects on the job performance of Agricultural instructors

The effect of job satisfaction on the performance of the instructor obtained a Critical Ratio (C.R) value of 2.750, which is greater than the cut off value of 1.96 or (2.750 > 1.96) at a significant level of 0.006 or less than 0.05 (0.006 < 0.05). Thus, it can be stated that job satisfaction has a significant effect on the performance of the instructor. The magnitude of the effect of job satisfaction on the performance of agricultural instructors in Pidie Regency is 0.289. This means that every 1% an increase in the value of job satisfaction, it will increase employee performance by 0.289%. These results support previous research conducted by Adigun et al. (2018); Platis et al., (2015) and Rozanna et al, (2019) stated that job satisfaction had a significant effect on the performance of the instructor. When employees feel satisfied at work, this will have an impact on improving their performance. Dissatisfaction or a low level of satisfaction with Agricultural Instructors can result in organizational disorganization because they

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are not motivated to do their best for the organization, on the other hand, Agricultural Instructors who get satisfaction in their work will lead to self-motivation to act to achieve individual achievements which will also result in organizational progress.

H₄ : Communication competence affects on job performance of agricultural extension workers

The effect of financial compensation on the performance of the instructor was obtained by the Critical Ratio (C.R) value of 2.146 which was greater than the cut off value of 1.96 or (2.146 > 1.96) at a significant level of 0.032 or less than 0.05 (0.032 < 0.05). Thus, it can be stated that financial compensation has a significant effect on the performance of the instructor. The magnitude of the effect of financial compensation on the performance of agricultural extension workers in Pidie Regency is 0.213. This means that every 1% there is an increase in the value of financial compensation, it will increase employee performance by 0.213%. These results support previous research conducted by Mabaso & Dlamini (2017); Yaseen, (2013); M.Baledi & Saed (2017); Darma & Supriyanto (2018) shows that the provision of financial compensation has a significant effect on employee job satisfaction. From these results, the better the provision of financial compensation in the form of a decent salary, performance allowances, health insurance, life, pensions and others, the more job satisfaction of Agricultural Extension workers will be.

H₅ : Communication competence affects on job performance of agricultural extension workers

The effect of communication competence on the performance of the instructor obtained a Critical Ratio (C.R) value of 2.650, which is greater than the cut off value of 1.96 or (2.650 > 1.96) at a significant level of 0.008 or less than 0.05 (0.008 < 0.05). Thus, it can be stated that communication competence has a significant effect on the performance of the instructor. The magnitude of the effect of financial compensation on the performance of agricultural extension workers in Pidie Regency is 0.239. This means that every 1% an increase in the value of communication competence will increase employee performance by 0.239%. The results of the study support previous research which shows that employee communication competence has a significant influence on employee performance. This discovery was put forward by (Darma & Supriyanto, 2018); (Nikolajevaite, Margarita & Sabaityte 2016); (Duwit, 2015); (Yu & Ko 2017) From these results, the more employees have skills in communicating with the community, the more job satisfaction of Agricultural Extension will increase.

Indirect Hypothesis Testing (Mediation)

Testing the mediation hypothesis was carried out to see whether the influence of exogenous variables, namely financial compensation and communication competence, had a significant effect on the performance of the instructor through job satisfaction. Partial Mediation or Full Mediation according to Baron and Kenny (1986)

H₆ : Job Satisfaction mediates of the relationship between Financial Compensation and Agricultural Extension Performance

The results of the indirect effect of financial compensation on the performance of the instructor through job satisfaction can be described as follows.

Figure 2. Financial Compensation - Job Satisfaction – Job Performance

These results can be explained that financial compensation has a significant effect on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction has a significant effect on the performance of the instructor and financial compensation has a direct and significant effect on the performance of the instructor, thus it is considered partial mediation. To prove that partial mediation is significant or not, it can be seen from the results of the mediation test through the Sobel test that a significant value of 0.024 is smaller than 0.05. The results of this study stated that the effect of financial compensation on the performance of the instructor was partially and

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significantly mediated by job satisfaction of 0.112%. The results of this study support research conducted by Darma & Supriyanto (2018); M. Baledi & Saed (2017). Employee satisfaction can mediate the effect of compensation on employee performance. From the results of this study indicate that, the provision of financial compensation in particular in the form of a decent salary, performance allowances, health insurance, life, and others, will have an indirect impact on employee performance through job satisfaction.

H₇ : Job Satisfaction mediates of the relationship between Communication Competence and Agricultural Extension Performance

The results of the indirect influence of communication competence on the performance of the instructor through job satisfaction can be described as follows.

Figure 3. Communication Competence - Job Satisfaction – Job Performance

These results can be explained that communication competence has a significant effect on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction has a significant effect on the performance of the instructor and communication competence has a direct and significant effect on the performance of the instructor, thus it is considered partial mediation. To prove that partial mediation is significant or not, it can be seen from the results of the mediation test through the Sobel test that a significant value of 0.075 is greater than 0.05. The results of this study stated that the influence of communication competence on the performance of the instructor was not significantly mediated by job satisfaction (non-mediation). The results of this study reject the research conducted by Lim et al, (2012) which states that the role of job satisfaction is important in mediating communication competence on performance.

Managerial Implications

The main factor that must be improved is employee job satisfaction. When employees feel satisfied at work, this will have an impact on improving their performance. Dissatisfaction or a low level of satisfaction with Agricultural Instructors can result in organizational disorganization because they are not motivated to do their best for the organization, on the other hand, Agricultural Instructors who get satisfaction in their work will lead to self-motivation to act to achieve individual achievements which will also result in organizational progress.

To increase employee job satisfaction, financial compensation must be considered and increased by management. Because, when the compensation received is better than before, it will trigger employee satisfaction at work. The better the provision of financial compensation in the form of a decent salary, performance allowances, health insurance, life, pensions and others, it will further improve the performance of Agricultural Extension.

To increase employee job satisfaction, communication competence also needs to be improved first. Employees who have good communication competence, tend to be easier to adapt in the workplace, the information conveyed also becomes more easily understood and accepted by farmers, so this will be a separate satisfaction for employees. The more employees have skills in communicating with the community, the more they will improve their performance as Agricultural Extension Officers.

The role of job satisfaction is important in mediating compensation given to employees to improve employee performance. Although the direct compensation given can improve performance, the role of job satisfaction cannot be denied.

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In other words, to improve the performance of management employees, they must jointly improve job satisfaction and the compensation given to agricultural extension workers.

Job satisfaction is known to not mediate the relationship of communication competence to employee performance. These results can be implied that the role of job satisfaction is not very important in mediating the relationship of communication competence of employees to improve their performance. Communication competence can directly improve performance. In other words, employees who have good competence will directly affect their performance without having to feel fast first.

CONCLUSION

Providing appropriate financial compensation can increase the job satisfaction of the extension workers. The communication competence of employees in carrying out their duties is closely related to the job satisfaction of the extension workers. The job satisfaction of the instructor can result in better performance of the instructor. Meanwhile, the provision of financial compensation will directly improve the performance of the agricultural instructor, as well as the communication skills of the agricultural instructor which will have a direct impact on the performance of the agricultural instructor. The indirect impact of job satisfaction is known to mediate (partial mediation) the relationship of financial compensation to the performance of agricultural extension workers. While on the relationship of communication competence to performance. Job satisfaction is known to be non-important (non-mediation).

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